

Search for Potent Anthelmintics—Part VII. Hydrazones Derived from 4-substituted-7-coumarinyl Oxyaceticacid Hydrazides

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Twenty new N-(4-substituted-7-coumarinyloxyacetyl) hydrazones have been synthesised as possible anthelmintic agents.

A number of hydrazones^{1,2,3} are known to possess strong anthelmintic activity. Also, compounds containing coumarin nucleus, viz. Asuntol and Haloxon⁴, have been found to be useful as effective anthelmintics. Hence, it was considered worth to synthesise the title hydrazones, anticipating that the presence of coumarin nucleus may induce considerable potency in them.

4-Substituted-7-hydroxy coumarin was refluxed with ethyl chloroacetate in the presence of dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate to furnish 4-substituted-7-O-(ethoxy carbonyl methyl) coumarin. The latter on condensation with hydrazine hydrate yielded the hydrazone, which on being refluxed with an appropriate aldehyde or ketone in the presence of absolute ethanol and a few drops of acetic acid afforded the desired hydrazones.

The anthelmintic screening of these compounds is in progress and the results will be published in due course.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer 577 in KBr pellets.

I 7-Hydroxy coumarin⁵ and 4-methyl-7-hydroxy coumarin⁶ were prepared according to published procedures.

II 4-Methyl-7-O-(ethoxycarbonylmethyl) coumarin and 7-O-(ethoxycarbonylmethyl) coumarin:

A mixture of an appropriate hydroxy coumarin (0.11 mole), anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.11 mole) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.11 mole) in anhydrous acetone (200 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 18 hr. The solvent was distilled off and

the residue triturated with cold water (100 ml). The solid obtained was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol. Analysis, melting points and spectral data of the compounds thus prepared are given as below:—

4-Methyl-7-O-(ethoxycarbonylmethyl) coumarin, m.p. 102°, yield 70% (Found: C, 64.36; H, 5.38%. Calculated for C₁₄H₁₄O₅: C, 64.12, H, 5.34%); 7-O-(Ethoxycarbonylmethyl) coumarin, m.p. 110°, yield 55% (Found: C, 62.73; H, 4.87%. Calculated for C₁₃H₁₂O₅: C, 62.90; H, 4.84%).

The I.R. spectra of both the above compounds showed bands at 1740 cm⁻¹ (ester), 1720 cm⁻¹ (lactone C=O) and 1120 cm⁻¹ (—CH—O—CH₂).

III 4-Methyl-7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazone and 7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazides:

0.1 mole of 4-(methyl or H)-7-O-(ethoxycarbonyl methyl) coumarin and 0.15 mole of hydrazine hydrate (99%) in absolute ethanol (100 ml) were refluxed on steam bath for 10 hr. Thereafter, the reaction mixture was concentrated, when a solid was obtained. It was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from water. The melting points and relevant data of the compounds so prepared are given as follows:—

4-Methyl-7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazone, m.p. 204°, yield 63% (Found: N, 11.24%. Calculated for C₁₃H₁₂O₄N₂: N, 11.29%); 7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazone, m.p. 184-6°, yield 60% (Found: N, 11.73%. Calculated for C₁₁H₁₀O₄N₂: N, 11.96%). Both of these hydrazides showed I.R. absorption bands at 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O of secondary amide), 3240 cm⁻¹ (N—H), 1730 cm⁻¹ (lactone C=O) and 1120 cm⁻¹ (—CH—O—CH₂).

* For correspondence.

TABLE 1—N-(4-SUBSTITUTED-7-COUMARINYLOXYACETYL) HYDRAZONES

S. No	R	-R ¹	R ²	M. P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen %	
							Found	Calcd.
1.	CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	272	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.61	7.56
2.	CH ₃	H	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	229	72	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.42	7.56
3.	CH ₃	H	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	236-7	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₆	7.18	7.33
4.	CH ₃	H	2-Furyl	234-6d	67	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₅	8.32	8.59
5.	CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	264	75	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅	7.68	7.95
6.	CH ₃	H	Phenyl	252	64	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	8.28	8.33
7.	CH ₃	H	2-Styryl	227	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄	7.51	7.73
8.	CH ₃	H	3,4-dimethoxy-6-nitrophenyl	254	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₆	9.37	9.52
9.	CH ₃	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	209	73	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.32	7.28
10.	CH ₃	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	238-9	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅	7.47	7.65
11.	CH ₃	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	199	65	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅	7.57	7.37
12.	CH ₃	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	232	62	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	11.38	11.51
13.	H	H	2-Styryl	168-9	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	8.23	8.05
14.	H	H	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	154-6	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆	7.38	7.61
15.	H	H	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	246	52	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₅	8.16	8.28
16.	H	H	Phenyl	233-5	57	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	8.49	8.69
17.	H	H	2-Furyl	209	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₅	8.93	8.97
18.	H	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	239	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.92	7.85
19.	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	211	61	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.43	7.56
20.	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	217	56	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅	7.63	7.95

d-decomposition

IV *N*-(4-Substituted-7-coumarinyloxyacetyl) hydrazones :

4-(Methyl or H)-7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazide (0.01 mole), aldehyde or ketone (0.01 mole), absolute ethanol (60 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2 or 3 drops) were refluxed on steam bath for 4 hr. Subsequent concentration and cooling of the reaction mixture gave a solid which was filtered, washed with hot water and recrystallised from dioxane or acetic acid.

The physical and analytical data of the prepared compounds are recorded in Table 1.

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